

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

PROPERTIES AND BIOREGULATORY ACTIVITY OF AZO COMPOUNDS

N. Valeeva,

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov, Uzbekistan,
100095, Universitetskaya st., 2, Tashkent

G. Usmanova,

Associate Professor, Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov, Uzbekistan,
100095, Universitetskaya st., 2, Tashkent

M. Ayupova,

Associate Professor, Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov, Uzbekistan,
100095, Universitetskaya st., 2, Tashkent

M. Aripdzhanova

Associate Professor, Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov, Uzbekistan,
100095, Universitetskaya st., 2, Tashkent
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898596>

Abstract

Dyes are products of fine organic synthesis obtained by combining various diazonium salts with derivatives of aromatic amines. They gave rise to the chemistry of pharmaceutical products, plant protection products, polymeric materials and other organic substances. Organic dyes are used in dyeing fabrics and yarns of various kinds: natural silk, wool, cotton, linen, artificial and synthetic fibers. A large number of synthetic dyes are known, and their number is constantly growing. They are used to dye leather, fur, wood, paper, various types of plastics, rubber, food products, they can be used in pharmaceuticals for dyeing medicines, etc. Most of the azo dyes are of low toxicity. We synthesized an azo dye based on a β -naphthol derivative and studied its properties. An analysis of the IR and UV spectra is given, and the bioregulatory activity of the obtained compound on cucumber and wheat seeds is studied. The resulting azo compound was found to have growth-stimulating activity.

Keywords: dye, organic synthesis, toxicity, biological activity, azo compound.

Introduction.

The joy of color perception is one of the oldest cultural and aesthetic feelings of mankind. Already in ancient times, people took care to dye their clothes and household items in beautiful colors. In religious rituals, on the contrary, they used eliminating repulsive colors.

Dyes are products of fine organic synthesis. They laid the foundation for the chemistry of pharmaceutical products, plant protection products, polymeric materials and many other branches of complex organic chemistry. Today, dyes do not occupy a dominant position in the chemical industry, but when it is necessary to create new original organic products, they again turn to aniline dye chemists who can design complex molecules and develop multi-stage technological processes.

Currently, the number of known azo dyes obtained by combining various diazonium salts with derivatives of aromatic amines and phenols is very large. The areas of application of organic dyes are very numerous and varied. They are used for dyeing yarn and fabrics of various types: linen, woolen, cotton, silk, artificial and synthetic fibers (more than 70% of total consumption). Organic dyes are used in pharmacy for coloring medicines, they are used to color skin, fur, wood, paper (more than 10%), inks for various purposes, creams, various types of plastics, rubber, food products, etc. About 10,000 types of synthetic dyes are known, and their number is constantly growing. About 900 thousand tons of dyes are produced in the world (this statistics does not include pigments, but includes optical

brighteners, which in some countries are considered textile auxiliaries). Every year a large number of new, more durable, bright and easy-to-use dyes appear, which replace obsolete ones.

Azo dyes are not very resistant to heating; already in the range of +100 - +250 ° C, they decompose. Substances containing NO₂ groups are explosive.

Most azo dyes are considered to be of low toxicity. Acute poisoning is extremely rare. Some types of dyes can cause skin irritation, eczema and dermatitis. Certain substances that have been proven to be toxic or carcinogenic have been phased out and replaced with safe alternatives. In the manufacture of azo dyes, in order to prevent diseases of workers in the industry, carcinogenic varieties and intermediates are gradually abandoned, replacing them with harmless analogues, in particular, due to carcinogenic properties, the use of 4-aminoazobenzene, 2-aminoazotoluene, fat-soluble dark red was discontinued.

Acute poisoning at work is rare, the most dangerous processes are filtration, grinding and drying, during which the dust of the dye enters the body through the respiratory tract and skin. Most of the azo dyes are excreted from the body with urine unchanged, some representatives come out in the form of salts, undergo dimethylation and oxidation.

The carcinogenicity of a number of compounds belonging to the described class is due to their chemical properties (aminoazotoluene and others), but other dyes

exhibit carcinogenic activity due to impurities of intermediates, such as 1-naphthylamine, dianisidine and benzidine. Certain varieties of the class also irritate the skin, which can lead to dermatitis and eczema, such activity is explained by impurities of nitroso compounds [1,2,3,4].

Along with toxic properties in the production of these compounds, azo dyes have positive properties in addition to their characteristic coloring function. Several dozen drugs are known in the world - derivatives of naphthols, ureas and carbamates, widely used in various sectors of the national economy, in agriculture, which determines the relevance of research. From this point of view, naphthol derivatives are of great interest as substances with various biological and pharmacological activities. In agriculture, they have found application as pesticides, herbicides, fungicides, insecticides, nematocides, growth stimulants, etc. In medicine, many azo compounds exhibit biological activity and are antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, and cytotoxic agents [5,6,7]. Azo compounds can be used as drug carriers and can also be prodrugs. A number of azo dyes are used in cell staining to visualize cellular components and metabolic processes [8]. They effectively inhibit the action of viruses, participate in most biological reactions in the body as inhibitors of nucleic acids, RNA and DNA, in protein synthesis, and are also used as anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and anticancer agents.

Methodology.

We have synthesized a dye based on a β -naphthol derivative [5,9]. In the synthesis, a catalyst, allyl ether, and an organic solvent were used in the following ratio, g:

β -naphthol derivative	10-15
Catalyst	6-10
Allyl bromide ether	4,8-25
organic solvent	Rest

Example of synthesis: 10 g of β -naphthol derivative and 6 g of catalyst, 4.8 g of allyl bromide, 100 ml of solvent were placed in a three-necked flask with a capacity of 500 ml, equipped with a stirrer, reflux condenser, thermometer and dropping funnel, and the mixture was heated to boiling for 1 hour with stirring. The reaction mixture was kept at 120°C for another 4 hours.

After cooling, the reaction mixture was extracted with diethyl ether, the ether extracts were combined, washed with distilled water, the ether layer was evaporated, the obtained azo compound was dissolved in the benzene:alcohol system 10:1. TLC was passed through chromatography, after the solvent was evaporated, the mass was collected - orange crystals. $T_m=114^\circ\text{C}$ (76.0% of theory). Solubility - acetone, benzene and alcohols.

Main part.

The study of the IR spectrum of the obtained compound (Fig. 1) contains specific absorption bands corresponding to the stretching vibrations of the bonds - OCH_2 1100-1260 cm^{-1} and C-H 1350-1465 cm^{-1} . In the regions of 3421-2926 cm^{-1} , there are absorption bands confirming the presence of $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}$ - groups. $=\text{CH}$ - also has a vibration band at 3020 cm^{-1} and absorption bands in the region of 1445-1460 cm^{-1} , 1000-675 cm^{-1} confirming the presence of the $=\text{CH}$ - group in the free state [9].

Fig.1. IR spectral analysis of an azo compound [9].

The IR spectrum contains characteristic absorption bands in the region of 1400-1500 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} corresponding to $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ groups of the azo compound.

The bending stretching vibrations of some aromatic groups appear as strong bands between the usual bending vibration bands in the region of 3000-3053 cm^{-1} and 1600-1500 cm^{-1} , the nature of the substitution is determined by strong absorption below 900 cm^{-1} . Overtone and composite frequency bands at 2000-1600 cm^{-1} are also sometimes used. Bands in the region 1225-950 cm^{-1} are of secondary importance.

The UV spectrum of the obtained compound (Fig. 2) has characteristic absorption bands in the region of 206, 226, 314, 418 and 479 nm.

A band appears in the spectrum due to the mono-substituted benzene ring in the region of 207 nm, and in the region of 226 nm a large bathochromic shift band of the naphthalene ring appears, at 290-320 nm due to azo groups. In the region of 416 nm, only one large band appears, which undergoes a bathochromic shift up to 481 nm. The condensed naphthalene core will mix the absorption maximum specific for aromatic compounds into the long-wave region and increase its intensity.

Fig.2. UV spectrum of an azo compound [9].

Biological growth-regulating activity.

Studying the alleged biological growth-regulating activity, laboratory tests of substances were carried out in the laboratory of phytotoxicology. Cucumber seeds (variety Orzu) were used as test objects for dicotyledonous weeds, and wheat (variety Tatyana) - for monocotyledonous weeds. Seeds of these crops meet a number of necessary requirements: seeds of wheat and cucumbers germinate together and give seedlings of similar size; seedlings are quite sensitive to the action of the tested substances and show clear differences in growth at comparable concentrations of chemical compounds; By evaluating these differences, it is possible to determine the physiological activity of the studied substances with sufficient accuracy [9,10,11].

During the tests, the method of Yu.V. Rakitin was used and Rudnik V.E. - "Primary biological evaluation

of chemical compounds as plant growth regulators and herbicides". The experiments were carried out in 4-fold repetition and laid down in 3 independent experiments. Based on the sum of the data of all experiments and their repetitions, calculations were made and conclusions were drawn.

Based on the data of photos and tables 1, 2, the synthesized azo compound showed the best activity in 0.001% concentration on monocots (wheat), which stimulated plant growth. The average length of the wheat root was 6.01 cm, while in the control it was 4.94 cm. On dicotyledonous plants (cucumbers), the azo compound showed good activity at 0.0001 and 0.00001% concentration. The growth of the root length in the variant was 8.43 and 8.33 cm, respectively, while in the control it was 6.94 cm.

Fig.3. Photo comparison of prototypes of the study growth-regulating activity of the azo compound [9].

Based on the data of photos and tables 1, 2, the synthesized azo compound showed the best activity in 0.001% concentration on monocots (wheat), which stimulated plant growth. The average length of the wheat root was 6.01 cm, while in the control it was 4.94

cm. On dicotyledonous plants (cucumbers), the azo compound showed good activity at 0.0001 and 0.00001% concentration. The growth of the root length in the variant was 8.43 and 8.33 cm, respectively, while in the control it was 6.94 cm.

Table 1.

Effect of azo compounds on the growth of wheat seedlings

Experience Options	Consumption rate concentrations %	The size of the measured parts of seedlings			
		Root length, cm	%	Stem height, cm	%
Control	H ₂ O, w/t	4,94	100	3,35	100
Azo compound ³	0,001	6,01	121,6	4,59	137
Azo compound ⁴	0,0001	4,73	-	3,27	-
Azo compound ⁵	0,00001	5,66	114,5	3,4	-
Azo compound ⁶	0,000001	5,9	119,4	1,26	-

Data of the report on scientific - research work are used [9].

Table 2.

Effect of azo compounds on the growth of cucumber seedlings

Experience Options	Consumption rate concentrations %	The size of the measured parts of seedlings			
		Root length, cm	%	Stem height, cm	%
Control	H ₂ O, w/t	6,94	100	1,99	100
Azo compound ³	0,001	7,31	105,3	2,03	102
Azo compound ⁴	0,0001	8,43	121,4	2,54	127,6
Azo compound ⁵	0,00001	6,35	-	2,41	121,1
Azo compound ⁶	0,000001	8,33	120	2,55	128,1

Data of the report on scientific - research work are used [9].

The percentage of average data was calculated in relation to the control. The table shows that the azo compound in 0.001% concentration exceeded the control variant. The length of the roots of wheat by 21.6%, the height of the stem by 37% of the control. On the seeds of cucumbers, the variant distinguished itself in 0.0001 and 0.00001% concentration, where the length of the roots exceeded the control by 21.4 and 27.6%, respectively, and the growth by 20 and 28.1%. Thus obtained azo compound has growth-promoting activity.

Conclusions.

Azo compounds exhibit biological activity and are antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal and cytotoxic agents, and can be used as drug carriers. Analysis of the IR and UV spectra of the obtained compound showed the presence of characteristic absorption bands in the region of 1400-1500 cm⁻¹ and 1600 cm⁻¹ corresponding to -N=N- groups of azo compounds specific for aromatic compounds. The azo compound has growth-promoting activity.

References:

1. Nazirov Z. Sh. Development of technology and synthesis of a derivative of nitro-substituted azophenol and its properties // *Young scientist*. 2012. No. 3. -S. 108-111.
2. Leung Wai-Yee, Cheung Ching-Ying, Yue Stephen. Modified carbocyanine dyes and their conjugates // US Patent 6974873, IPC C 07 B 209/02. Appl. 01.10.2001; publ. December 13, 2005, NPK 548/455.
3. Reiher Uwe, Redemonte Ron. Fiber-active azo dyes, processes for their production, use // *Application* 28.12.1999; publ. 01/23/2001.
4. Valeeva N.G., Ayupova M.B., Usmanova G.A., Aripdzhanova M.A. Synthesis and study of allyl

dyes// IV international scientific conference. Tokyo. Japan. 27-28.04.2023.

5. Makhsumov A.G., Valeeva N.G., Nabiev U. A., Ismailov B.M. Synthesis of new bromine acetylene dithiocarbamates derivatives and their growth-stimulating activity // *Journal of Critical Reviews* ISSN-2394-5125 Vol 7, Issue 4, 2020, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.04.20>, pp.113-119.

6. Makhsumov A.G., Valeeva N.G., Holboyev Y.Kh., Abdurakhmanov U.K., Boltabaev K.K. Synthesis, properties of the n, n1 -hexamethylene bis - [(diethylamino) -urea] derivative and its application // *Journal Solid State Technology*. ISSN- 2394-5125 Vol 63, Issue 1S, 2020, DOI, pp.1640-1653.

7. Makhsumov A.G., Valeeva N. G., Khaitov Zh. K., Khamidova V. Dj. Syntheses, the biological activity of bis-aromatic urea derivatives // *The Multidisciplinary Journal of Educational Research*. Hipatia Press. 20th December 2021. ISSN: 2014-2862. DOI: 10.4526/remie.2021.94557. P.302-317.

8. Oakenfull D. J. *Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.* 11 1973, 1006.

9. Report on scientific - research work. Synthesis of coloring substances based on allylazine compounds and study of the kinetics of obtaining, regularities of the process, 2018, Tashkent, p.115

10. Makhsumov A.G., Zhuraeva Sh.D., Valeeva N.G., Tillaev A.T. Synthesis of 1-phenyl-azo-β-allyl ester of naphthol // *J. Chemistry and chemical technology*, Tashkent, 2018, No. 2, S. 21-23

11. Makhsumov A.G., Valeeva N.G., Kurbanova M.A. Synthesis based on 1-phenyl-azo-naphthol-1 and its chemical properties // *Vestnik NUUZ*, Tashkent, 2017. V.2. pp.433-437.